

METHODS OF IMPROVING STUDENT-CENTERED AND COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACHES IN ENGLISH CLASSES

Khidirbaev Sherali Yeralievich

Teacher of "Interfaculty foreign languages" department, Faculty of Philology, Gulistan State
University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7725850>

Abstract. *Person-oriented education, by its essence, provides for the full development of all participants of the educational process. This means that when designing education, it is necessary to approach based on the learning goals related to the future professional activity, not the personality of a specific learner.*

Keywords: *person-oriented education, pedagogical technology, foreign language, efficiency, expert, goal.*

Today, the main focus is on the student, his personality and unique inner world. Therefore, the main goal of a modern teacher is to choose methods and forms of organization of educational activities students that optimally correspond to the set goal of personal development. In recent years, the issue of using new information technologies in schools has been raised more and more. It is not only new technical means, but also new forms and methods of teaching, a new approach to the educational process. The main goal of teaching foreign languages is to form and develop the communicative culture of schoolchildren, to teach them to practice a foreign language.

Teaching technology as a pedagogical strategy will have tools to activate and accelerate the activity of students and teachers. Such technologies include:

1. Pedagogy of cooperation
2. Pedagogical technology based on keeping the personality in the pedagogical process (Sh.A. Amonashvili technology);
3. Technology of accelerating teaching of educational material based on schemes and models (V.F. Shatalov technology);
4. On the basis of effective management and organization of the educational process, built technology (S.N. Lisenkova technology, N.P. Guzik's teaching system planning technology);
5. Technology of individualization of teaching (Inge Unt, A.S. Graniskaya, V.D. Shadrikov technology)

Collaborative pedagogy Collaborative pedagogy began to develop in the 80s of the 20th century and brought to life many innovative processes in education. This technology is based on the experience of well-known Russian and foreign pedagogues.

Sh.A. Amonashvili's human-person technology. In his experimental school, he developed and implemented cooperative pedagogy, personal approach, excellent pedagogy of language and mathematics teaching.

The main goals of Sh.A. Amonashvili are as follows:

1. It is not possible to form, develop and educate a noble person by showing the child's personal qualities;
2. To glorify the child's soul and heart;
3. Development and formation of the child's cognitive abilities;
4. To create conditions for obtaining broad and deep knowledge and qualifications;

5. Ideal education is self-education. Sh.A. Amonashvili used the following methods and methodical methods to implement his technology: he is humanitarian; it is a personal approach; it is an additional possibility of family pedagogy; it is an educational activity. It is a communication skill; In Sh.A. Amonashvili's technology, assessment of child's activity is of particular importance. The use of grades is very limited. Emphasis is placed on qualitative rather than quantitative assessment, i.e. description, outcome package, self-assessment.

Language is the main means of communication, without which it is difficult to imagine the existence and development of human society. Today, at a time when there are great changes in social relations in our world, information media require the improvement of students' communicative skills, they can exchange ideas in different situations, learn the norms of language and speech in the process of interacting with other participants of communication. requires proper use. In such conditions, the main purpose of a foreign language is the formation of communicative ability, that is, it requires the implementation of interpersonal and intercultural communication in a foreign language.

At this stage of higher education, there are important changes that cover almost all aspects of the pedagogical process. They set specific goals and tasks for the educational process. One of the main tasks is to improve the teacher's pedagogical skills by mastering modern teaching and learning technologies. With the use of any new technologies, new pedagogical ideas of the teacher begin. The most important task of the educational process is the student's personal interest, it is necessary to know which technologies should be used in the educational process to obtain the planned results. The use of any specific educational technology, no matter how perfect, does not create effective conditions for determining and developing students' skills.

Pedagogical technology refers to a well-thought-out model of educational-pedagogical activities together with a comfortable environment for teachers and students to design, organize and conduct the educational process.

The use of modern teaching technologies makes it possible to make the teaching process uniform and achieve high efficiency. Now let's talk briefly about why personal-oriented technologies are becoming relevant today, why these technologies are the present day and future of education, and their essence.

In this teaching technology, the attitude of pedagogy to the student has an authoritarian character, that is, in the process of education, he appears as the only subject, and students only act as objects. In other words, the student's initiative and independence are almost lost in the authoritarian teaching technology, teaching is carried out in a compulsory way. The main unit of training in the classroom-lesson system, which is still the most widespread in the world, is a lesson, which is devoted to one subject of one subject and is led by a teacher. The task of the teacher is to create conditions for practical mastery of the language for each student, to choose such teaching methods that allow each student to demonstrate his activity and creativity. The task of the teacher is to activate the cognitive activity of the student in the process of teaching foreign languages. Modern pedagogical technologies, such as collaborative learning, project methodology, use of new information technologies, Internet resources, help to implement a person-oriented approach in the educational process, individualization and differentiation of teaching, taking into account the abilities of children, their level of learning, provides.

Forms of working with computer training programs in foreign language classes include: learning vocabulary; practice pronunciation; teaching dialogic and monologic speech; teaching

writing; development of grammatical events. The possibilities of using Internet resources are huge. The Global Internet provides conditions for students and teachers located anywhere in the world to get any information they need: regional geographical materials, news in the life of young people, articles from newspapers and magazines, etc. A number of didactic problems can be solved using the Internet in English in lessons: formation of reading skills and competencies using global network materials; improving the writing ability of schoolchildren; filling students' vocabulary; formation of students' motivation to learn English. In addition, this work aims to explore the possibilities of Internet technologies to expand the horizons of schoolchildren, establish and maintain business relations and contacts with peers in English-speaking countries.

The meaningful basis of mass computerization is related to the fact that the modern computer is an effective tool for optimizing the conditions of mental work, in general, in any of its forms. The computer has one characteristic that defines its use as a tool for teaching others and as an aid in the acquisition of knowledge, and that is its inanimate nature. The machine can have a "friendly" relationship with the user and sometimes "support" him, but he will never show signs of anger and will not let you feel bored. In this sense, the use of computers is perhaps most useful in individualizing some aspects of teaching. The main goal of learning a foreign language at school is the formation of communicative competence, all other goals (education, training, development) are implemented in the process of realizing this main goal.

Communicative approach includes communication training and the formation of intercultural communication skills, which are the basis of Internet activities. Without communication, the Internet has no meaning - it is an international multinational, intercultural society, whose life is based on the electronic communication of millions of people around the world, talking at the same time - this is the number and size of the participants in it. the biggest conversation on. Attending a foreign language class for him, we create a real communication model.

Currently, communication, interactivity, authenticity of communication, language learning in cultural context, autonomy and humanitarianism of education are given priority. These principles allow the development of intercultural competence as a component of communicative competence. The ultimate goal of teaching foreign languages is to teach a free orientation in a foreign language environment and the ability to adequately respond to different situations, i.e. contact Today, new methods using Internet resources are opposed to traditional foreign language teaching.

To teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create real, real-life situations that stimulate the learning of the material and develop adequate behavior (that is, the so-called principle of communication authenticity). New technologies, especially the Internet, are trying to correct this error.

Communicative approach is a strategy that simulates communication aimed at conscious understanding of the material and methods of working with it, creating psychological and linguistic preparation for communication. It is not particularly difficult for the user to implement a communicative approach on the Internet. A communicative task should invite students to discuss a problem or question, students not only exchange information, but also evaluate it. The main criterion that allows distinguishing this approach from other types of educational activities is that students independently choose linguistic units to form their thoughts. In the communicative

approach, the use of the Internet is highly encouraged: its purpose is to interest students in learning a foreign language by accumulating and expanding their knowledge and experience.

One of the main requirements for teaching foreign languages using Internet resources is to create interaction in the lesson, which is usually called interactivity in the methodology. Interactivity is "combining, coordinating, and complementing communicative goals and resulting efforts by means of speech." By teaching the real language, the Internet helps to build speaking skills and abilities, and also ensures genuine interest and therefore effectiveness in teaching vocabulary and grammar. Interactivity not only creates real situations from life, but also forces students to give appropriate answers to them in a foreign language.

One of the technologies that provide student-centered education is the project method as a method of developing creativity, knowledge activity, and independence. The typology of projects is diverse. Projects can be divided into monoprosjects, collective, oral, concrete, written and Internet projects. In actual practice, it is often necessary to deal with research projects, mixed projects with creative, practice-oriented and informational features. Project work is a multifaceted approach to language learning, covering reading, listening, speaking and grammar. The project method helps to develop active independent thinking of students and directs them to joint research work. In my opinion, project-based learning teaches children to cooperate, and learning to cooperate instills moral values such as mutual aid and empathy, builds creativity and activates students.

In general, the inseparability of teaching and education is observed in the process of teaching the project. The project method develops students' communication skills, culture of behavior, the ability to form thoughts concisely and easily, tolerance of the opinions of communication partners, the ability to receive information from various sources, process using modern computer technologies, contribute to the emergence of natural needs creates a language environment that grows.

In the course of foreign languages, the project method can be used within the program materials of almost any subject.

REFERENCES

1. Johnson, K. E. The Sociocultural Turn and Its Challenges for Second Language Teacher Education. // TESOL Quarterly., – London., 2006.
2. Harmer J. The Practice of English Language Teaching. – London., 2001.
3. Indiaminov N. and others. Person-oriented education in improving educational efficiency. Educational technologies. 2014(8).
4. Sherov, D. (2020). Succession Issues in Teaching English. Academic Research in Educational Sciences, (3).
5. Rahim, A., & Doston, S. (2020). IMPROVING THE CONVERSATIONAL PROCESS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING. International Engineering Journal For Research & Development, 5(1), 6-6.
6. Makhmudov, K. (2021). Effective methods of teaching reading in English language lessons. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(3).